

The Islamic State and the crises of COVID 19

Forewords

In a speech in Somalia, Muslim cleric Fuad Mohamed Khalaf, a member of al-Shabaab, said that "Muslims should be happy with the suffering of the infidels" and stressed that the coronavirus "exposed the weaknesses of the United States and its allies".

For Elisabeth Kendall, the fight against IS will have to go even more through the monitoring of a wide and diffuse space, which this terrorist group used with an efficiency and reach so far unmatched among terrorist organizations: the internet.

That is why he argues that the surveillance of propaganda by this and other terrorist groups is important - especially those in Europe. "Whoever is not reading and watching their advertising, will not understand their aspirations", he stresses. "Now that they have nowhere to dream of, as they did with Raqqa, the internet has become even more of their essential ground."

Islamic State spokesman Abu Hamza al-Qurashi makes reference to the "harassment" against the "Muslims" in Mosul (Iraq) and Al-Baguz (Syria), which caused "death and destruction" in the wings of the group.

"We are happy with the torture of the supreme god (...) and we ask him for more torture (...) unless [the infidels] choose the path of fidelity," added the spokesman. "Many of you have lost everything," he added.

The 40-minute audio message, the group's unusual form of communication, was released in the context where the security forces in Iraq and Syria are intensifying attacks on positions of the group, which no longer controls the territory in those two countries where established a "caliphate" in 2014.

"The suspension of global coalition operations (especially in Iraq) has left a power vacuum that the Islamic State is trying to exploit. Being autonomous and living in remote hiding places, ISIS is already socially isolated and well prepared for confinement", points out the report.

According to EASO, jihadists will be able to take advantage of the fact that local military forces are "poorly equipped and 'distracted' with disaster assistance and curfews" in the framework of the covid-19 pandemic to regroup and return to being more active in much of the region, despite having recently lost their leader, Abu Bakr al-Baghdadi, killed in an American attack.

In the latest issue of al-Naba, a magazine edited by the group for its followers, an infographic was published with some recommendations, including a request for

terrorists to avoid travel to Europe, the United States, China and other countries affected by the disease.

According to the Homeland Security Today website, the statement lists "guidelines for dealing with the epidemic". For the Islamic State, the main advice is "to trust God and take refuge in Him from disease", but followers have an "obligation" to take protective measures to prevent it.

Among these measures, the terrorist group emphasizes that "the healthy should not enter the land of the epidemic and the sick must not leave it". According to the council, terrorists should not travel to Europe and the United States, which are common targets in the West, nor to countries in the Middle East such as Iran, Iraq and Saudi Arabia.

The group dominates provinces and has active cells in some countries still free of the disease, such as the Central and West Africa region, as well as Syria and Yemen, where civil war makes it difficult to collect information about epidemics. But cases have already been confirmed in Algeria, Egypt, Iraq, Afghanistan, India, the Philippines and Indonesia.

The reorganization in Africa of ISIS - Evolution and progression in Mozambique

In Mozambique, according to statements by the President of the Republic and the Minister of Defence, there are groups of terrorists in the district of Cabo Delgado and other groups in the centre, but who are considered to be affected by RENAMO.

The situation is complicated because as these groups demonstrate, they show all the characteristics of IS members.

However, for better clarification, we analyze the theory of armed groups:

A –

What constitutes an armed group? How many are there? How should they be differentiated from each other and categorized? What motivates them? To what extent do they cooperate with each other, as well as with states and other non-state actors?

Can they be identified and tackled in their emerging or incipient stage of development? Do armed groups offer political opportunities as well as threats to politics? There is no taxonomy that rigorously addresses these issues, even though armed groups are the subject of increasing attention worldwide. Consider how the Non-State Actors Working Group (NSAWG), a unit of the International Committee to Ban Landmines (ICBL), divides armed groups into the following categories: "rebel groups, irregular armed groups, insurgents, dissident armed forces, guerrillas ,

Liberation movements and de facto territorial government bodies ". It is not very strict! What is the difference between insurgents and guerrillas or irregular armed groups and dissident armed forces? And can't a liberation movement be a de facto territorial governing body? The NSAWG identifies approximately "170 armed non-state actors worldwide". In doing so, he notes that "the ideology, objectives, strategies, form and level of organization, grassroots support, legitimacy and degree of international recognition," these groups "vary widely." That is correct.

However, what is interesting is not only the various groups included, but the excluded ones. For example, there are no organized criminal groups; Nor does Al Qaeda, a transnational terrorist organization, appear on the NSAWG list. Claude Bruderlein, director of the Harvard Program on Humanitarian Policy and Conflict Research, also notes that "armed groups differ considerably, from Mafias-like militias to religious movements and corporate armies," making common definition difficult.

Claude Bruderlein proposes that he qualifies as an armed group, one that meets the following criteria must: [First] combatants are organized according to a unitary command structure and ... commanders have at least a minimum of control over conduct combatants. [Secondly], the group is involved in a political struggle ... to redefine the political and legal base of society through the use of violence. [Finally], armed groups are independent of state control.

Here again, this definition excludes several types of armed groups. For example, not all armed groups seek to "redefine the political and legal base of society through the use of violence". Clans and tribes in places like Afghanistan that seek to maintain the status quo. And not all armed groups "are organized according to a unitary command structure." This is certainly true for Al Qaeda, as well as many of the militias in failed states like Somalia and the Democratic Republic of Congo.

In addition, some armed groups are under the influence of a state. Consider Hezbollah in Lebanon, sponsored by Iran and Syria. The Federation of American Scientists (FAS) describes armed groups - which he calls Para-States - as entities that contest the "monopoly of the state on the use of violence within a specific geographic territory ". FAS maintains profiles for 387 of these organizations.

To be included in the list, a par state or armed group must have used force, defined by the FAS as some form of "direct action or armed struggle". Unlike the previous examples, those who developed the Para-State list "Launch a wide network" ranging from "criminal companies, like substance distribution networks", "national liberation movements", as well as those "involved in the terrorism ".

While these efforts to identify and define armed groups are steps in the right direction, a more parsimonious taxonomy is needed. We propose one to divide armed groups into four categories - insurgents, terrorists, militias and organized crime.

- First, here's what they have in common. One all armed groups, to varying degrees, challenge the state's authority, power and legitimacy. Some seek to do so, overthrowing the government and replacing it, while other armed groups try to weaken, manipulate or co-opt the state.

- Second, armed groups, at least in part, use violence and force, whether in unconventional and asymmetric ways. It is true that some armed groups maintain political and paramilitary wings, and that the former can, for tactical reasons, avoid violence.

Still, the use of force is a critical tool for these organizations, regardless. Violence is used instrumentally to achieve political and / or other goals.

- Third, armed groups operate both locally and globally due to developments in the information age, a point elaborated below. They are able to expand the battlefield to attack state opponents both at home and abroad.

- Finally, as mentioned above, armed groups are not democratically structured organizations. They do not adhere to the rule of law to resolve disputes. The opposite is the case. These common characteristics that resist, insurgents, terrorists, militias and criminal organizations have many important differences between them. There is no generic or ideal type for any of these four variants. This is certainly true in terms of the basic characteristics of an armed group, which can be divided into the following six elements:

- 1) Leadership;
- 2) Classification and file adhesion;
- 3) Organizational structure and functions;
- 4) Ideology / political code of beliefs and objectives;
- 5) Strategy and tactics;
- 6) Links with other non-state and state actors.

How armed groups address each of these issues varies across and within the four categories of taxonomy. Below each of the armed groups contained in the taxonomy are defined, and the main differences between them are highlighted.

1 - Insurgents:

Insurgents can threaten the state with complex political and security challenges because of how they organize and operate. One expert defines insurgents as armed groups that "consciously use political resources and violence to destroy, reshape or

sustain the basis for the legitimacy of one or more aspects of politics". Although a useful starting point, we propose a more comprehensive outline: insurgency is a prolonged political and military set of activities aimed at gaining partial or total control over a country's territory through the use of irregular military forces and illegal political organizations. Insurgents engage in actions ranging from guerrilla operations, terrorism and sabotage to political mobilization, political action, intelligence / counterintelligence activities and psychological propaganda / warfare. All of these instruments are designed to weaken and / or destroy the power and legitimacy of a governing government, while increasing the power and legitimacy of the armed insurgent group. Within the parameters of this definition, insurgent groups take on various organizational forms ranging from complex political, intelligent and military dimensions to closely structured conspiratorial groups.

The classic insurgent model is designed to mobilize supporters and establish an alternative political authority for the existing government, by employing intelligence and military means to attack and weaken the state through escalating violence.

The narrower conspiracy variation, on the other hand, focuses more exclusively on the use of violence to undermine a government's will to sustain losses and remain in the struggle, rather than in the control of a given territory and the construction of a parallel political apparatus.

It also affects the approach taken by insurgents is the area or terrain in which they carry out their activities. They can occur in an urban and / or rural environment, as well as transnational. Each of these locations will have an impact on how insurgents approach each of the characteristics or elements of an armed group identified above, organization, ideology, motivation, leadership, member formation.

Where armed insurgent groups operate, the objectives they pursue and the organizational approach they will adopt will shape the strategy employed.

2 - Terrorists:

Terrorism and the armed groups that employ it have been defined in several ways. In addition, since the last "terrorism" of the 1970s, it has often been used in a pejorative way to discredit and delegitimize.

A more operational definition is proposed: terrorism is the deliberate creation and exploitation of fear by an armed group through the threat and / or use of the most proscribed type of violence for political purposes, whether for or in opposition to an established government.

The act is designed to have a far-reaching psychological effect beyond the immediate target of the attack and to instil fear and intimidate a wider audience.

The targets of terrorist groups are increasingly non-combatants, and a large number of them, who, under international standards, have the status of protected individuals and groups.

Terrorists differ from insurgents in several ways. Important distinctions can be seen in tactics and segmentation. Insurgents use a range of political and paramilitary tactics, of which terrorism is often just one.

Terrorist groups, on the other hand, have a narrower operational approach that is increasingly focusing on finding non-combatants.

During the 1990s, terrorist groups were progressively more indiscriminate in their targets, seeking to kill as many protected groups as possible.

As with insurgents, terrorist groups in the 1990s were motivated more by ethnicity and religion.

According to RAND-St. The Andrews University index, approximately half of all known terrorist groups has been religiously focused. The overwhelming majority of these groups are located in the Islamic world.

Another important difference between armed terrorist groups and insurgents is the extent to which the former establish ties and cooperation agreements. During the 1990s, Al Qaeda created an elaborate set of connections with a significant number of similar terrorist groups in up to 60 countries.

Indeed, Al Qaeda has established a multinational alliance between armed groups that can operate in the original and transnational states.

It has also developed a sophisticated financial network to raise and transfer money to the organization and its operations. As with an insurgent movement, there are incipient indicators, identifiable by the state, of a terrorist group's ability to mount a serious threat against it. However, given that some terrorist groups can be quite small, this is difficult.

However, these groups still need to establish a clandestine organization, recruit and train staff, acquire resources, know and communicate, and so on. While they do this in secret, however, these activities can be monitored.

As more is learned about Al Qaeda's origins, early stages and maturation, it becomes evident that there were early warning indicators for the intelligence community to collect and analyze.

3 - Militias:

With the growing number of weak and failing states, a third category of armed groups - militias - became more important and prominent in the 1990s. They seemed to thrive, in particular, in states with ineffective central governments and benefiting from a black market that facilitates its growth. The individual militias received considerable international attention; in particular those from Africa and Central Asia, there were few attempts to define this type of armed group systematically or to identify different subtypes.

What is a militia? Below, we propose a broad definition. Based on post-Cold War examples, armed militia groups appear to share the following characteristics: A militia in today's context is an irregular armed force recognizable that operates in the territory of a weak and / or bankrupt state.

Militia members generally come from the lower classes and tend to be composed of young males who are attracted to this milieu because it gives them access to money, resources, power and security. Often they are forced to join; in other cases, it is seen as an opportunity or a duty.

Militias may represent specific ethnic, religious, tribal, clan or other community groups. They can operate under the auspices of a factional leader, clan or ethnic group, or on their own after the disruption of state forces. They can also be at the service of the state, directly or indirectly.

Generally, militia members do not receive formal military training. However, in some cases, they are skilled unconventional fighters. In other cases, they are nothing more than a gang of extremely violent bandits that feed on the civilian population.

4 - Organized criminal groups.

The final category of the armed group is that of organized crime. While it is certainly not new, it has grown in importance as a dangerous threat to individual states and the international system. The wealth and power of these organizations has grown over the past 25 years and several have established international links and networks.

Armed criminal groups today exhibit the following characteristics:

- First, they have an identifiable structure and leadership whose purpose is to operate outside the law in a particular criminal activity. They maintain hierarchical groups with clearly demarcated leadership - subordinate functions, through which the group's objectives are advanced. As these armed groups mature, they no longer rely on the leadership of one or a few individuals for their survival.

- Second, these armed groups can take different forms and "operate over time [and space] not just for ephemeral [or temporary] purposes". That is, they are involved in

more than one type of criminal enterprise and operate in large parts of a region or globally.

- Third, armed criminal groups maintain internal cohesion and loyalty through their members' ethnicity and family ties. They are anchored in a "community, family or ethnic base". This provides the armed group with a code of behavior that implies "fidelity, rituals, ethnic ties ... [to] help involve the compliance and loyalty of individuals within the organization". These "bonding bonds" allow group members to trust each other in very personal ways, reducing the likelihood that the officer will infiltrate the group.

- Fourth, criminal organizations employ violence "to promote and protect their interests". It can be directed externally against rivals to intimidate or eliminate them as competitors. Internally, it maintains discipline and loyalty. While criminal organizations vary in the extent to which they employ violence, all do so "for commercial purposes". If violence is the stick, criminal organizations also use bribery carrots. The availability of large amounts of money are used to corrupt the police and other government officials, enticing them to look the other way.

- Finally, each of these characteristics contributes to the characteristic that distinguishes criminal organizations from other armed groups - they seek to maximize their profits, as well as a legitimate business.

The pursuit of money and the power that goes with it propel and sustain armed criminal groups. Based on the five characteristics described above, the following definition is proposed: an armed criminal group has a hierarchical structure and clandestine or secret leadership, whose main objective is to operate outside the law in a particular criminal company.

These groups often engage in more than one type of criminal activity and can operate in large areas of a region and globally.

Often, these groups have a family or ethnic base that improves the cohesion and security of their members. These armed groups generally maintain their position through the threat or use of violence, corruption of public officials, grafting or extortion.

The widespread political, economic, social and technological changes taking place in the world allow organized crime groups to pursue their penultimate objective - to make as much money as possible from illegal activities - in ways that their previous colleagues have not been able to.

The main international criminal organizations (ICO) have established links with other armed groups and not just criminals. One of the most significant developments since

the end of the Cold War is the increased involvement of insurgents, terrorists and militia groups in criminal activities. Unable to rely on outside help from state sponsors, who can be fleeting, many insurgents and terrorists

Groups diversify their resource base by engaging with international criminal organizations. For ICOs, these partnerships are equally valuable, expanding the scope and profitability of their operations. An example of this is Hezbollah. Although Iran provides significant assistance, Hezbollah is involved in drug trafficking as another way to finance its activities.

It provides opioid and overflow protection to criminal organizations in exchange for financial support and other types of support. In Afghanistan, several armed ethnic groups are involved in similar activities, as was Al Qaeda.

An example can be found in Africa. Since the late 1980s, the National Union for the Total Independence of Angola (UNITA) and the United Revolutionary Front (RUF) in Sierra Leone have paid for the costs of their armed struggles with mining and illegal diamond exports through agreements with international criminal unions.

The problem of looting and illegal exploitation of minerals by ICOs, among others, is perhaps best exemplified in the ongoing war of more than 30 years in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC-ex Zaire). However, an additional link that improves the power of ICOs is The active partnership between political actors - the officials and staff of the legal-government establishment of state and criminal actors.

These arrangements are called the political-criminal nexus (PCN). It consists of different degrees of cooperation between political participants and criminals at the local, national and transnational levels. An example of such a link is the relationship between Victor Bout, one of the largest illegal arms traders in the world and different governments and rebel groups across Africa. Bout used the states of Liberia, Equatorial Guinea and Central African Republic to register his plane. Your organization has purchased end-user certificates for tons of weapons from the governments of Burkina Faso, Togo and Côte d'Ivoire.

And he supplied not only small arms, but to attack helicopters to the Taylor regime in Liberia, anti-aircraft weapons for the RUF in Sierra Leone and sophisticated mines and artillery for UNITA in Angola. Payment for weapons was often in the form of diamonds by rebel groups.

B -

Cabo Delgado, a region where megaprojects for the extraction of natural gas are advancing, has had frequent attacks by armed groups classified as a terrorist threat since October 2017.

Mozambican authorities account for a total of 162,000 people affected by armed violence. At least 550 people have died from violence since 2017. Thus we analyze the Mozambican phenomenon:

The enemy's modus operandi is evolving and becoming more and more sophisticated, attacking even war artefacts (vehicles, motorcycles and the military themselves).

- In the beginning, they based their actions around the Islamic religion, growing a beard and wearing a turban.
- When armed attacks began, on 5 and 6/10/2017, against Vila Sede in the district of Mocímboa da Praia, Mueda, Nangade and Palma, armed groups started attacks on strategic targets, namely:
 - Agents of the defence and security forces;
 - Police units and subunits;
 - Civilian populations, public and private institutions;

As a result, they vandalized and destroyed several properties (mainly residences and vehicles) using arson, bladed weapons and firearms forcing the massive displacement of populations to safe places.

The Armed Groups had the initial intention of occupying this place militarily and administratively and dismembering it from the country, where the intention was to introduce the administrative system of Caliphate and the most radical form of Islamic law of

The events taking place in some districts of the Province of Cabo Delgado are *suis generis* and threaten, on the one hand, national sovereignty and, on the other, challenge the Mozambican State to better understand and outline better solutions for managing the situation and for vigorous intervention maintaining internal security.

1 -

There are two positions: the first advocates that this is the fundamentalist Islamic group called Al Shahabab means youth and the second, that it is a group called Ahlu sunnah wa-jamâ which means followers of the good customs and practices of the last prophet Mohammad, that is , one should not practice evil actions or that distort the principles of the prophet Mohammad.

Elements of the Islamic State refugees did not come out as a group, mixing between these two.

It was found that similar acts also occurred in Tanzania, on 2 and 3 October 2017, identical groups attacked the police stations in Lindi and Kilomba, in Ntunara Province.

It should be noted that these armed groups operating in Mozambique also operate in Tanzania, especially in the Tanga region.

Given the geographic location with Mozambique, the actions branched out to some districts in the Province of Cabo Delgado with some extensions to Niassa, Nampula and Zambezia.

This phenomenon dates back to 2011. However, it was the attacks of 5 October 2017 that attracted the attention of the Mozambican authorities to be a group organized with the scope of disturbing Public Order and Tranquillity.

It should be noted that, the first indications occurred in the village of Nakhole, district of Balama. In this district, fundamentalists wearing the cloak of a religious sect already propagated social disorder by instructing the public not to follow government programs, prohibiting children from attending public schools and privileging the teaching of the Koran.

In 2012, in the District of Palma, there was the arrival of individuals from Tanzania with the aim of exchanging or exchanging experiences of Islam. However, from the interaction between the Mozambican and Tanzanian police, it was found that it was a group dangerous and with an ideology similar to the group that was in the district of Balama, a fact that justified their repatriation as a precautionary measure.

An example is the ban on joining the water program for the community, characterized by the construction of water holes.

It should be noted that the intervention of the Defence and Security Forces contributed to the slowdown of this phenomenon that resurfaced in 2014, 2015 and 2016 almost simultaneously, in the districts of Mocímboa da Praia, Palma and Chiúre. However, in 2017 there was a resurgence of violent actions and changes in order caused by these groups, mainly in the district of Macomia.

It was found that the phenomenon was introduced in Mozambique by individuals of Tanzanian origin, Ethiopia and Syria, assisted by national citizens.

2 -

The investigations carried out lead us to conclude that evildoers benefit from internal and external financing, especially from Islamic countries.

- Much of the group's leadership has ties to religious, commercial and military circles, radical Islamist groups in Tanzania, Somalia, Iraq, Syria, Kenya and the Great Lakes region;

- To differentiate itself from other practitioners of Islam at the local level, the group has its own attire: its members wear a white turban around their heads; shaved hair; big beard, smock and short black pants, just below the knee.
- In their composition, in the action groups, these have been in uniform with the campaign uniform and armed with firearms although in small quantities and the others civilian armed with bladed weapons (machetes and bow and arrows).
- In the group there are demobilized police and military personnel (e.g. group leader in Nangade was ex-Commandos and ex-Border Guard Police).
- They live in some villages, where their collaborators, relatives and family members are also, who keep them informed of situations of operational interest, especially actions or physical presence of the FADM.

3 -

- In a first phase, the group had a structure based on cells, managed by its religious leaders;
- The cells were relatively autonomous and with flexible chains of command. Despite this, the link with the group's central command remained strong;
- The organization has multiple cells, units, divisions and figures with different powers;
- The autonomy of the cells makes it possible for each leader to outline and follow his own strategy, thus managing, autonomously, the areas under his authority... This allows the capture or death of a leader does not significantly affect the operability of the group. On the other hand, it also allows a better adjustment to the context.

4 -

Internal and external recruitment:

- From the analysis of data and information collected on the ground, it was found that a considerable part were recruited internally, in the coastal districts of the Provinces of Cabo Delgado, namely, Mocímboa da Praia and Macomia, and Nampula, in Memba and Nacala.

It should be noted that most of the recruits were residents of the Macomia district, in the areas of Rweia, Cogolo and Inguane, administrative posts in Mucojo and Quiterajo. Likewise, there was external recruitment in Tanzania, a country bordering Mozambique in the north and in other countries such as Burundi, Congo, Somalia and Kenya. Islamic State members have fled refugees from Syria and Iraq.

Recruitment and advertising means employed

- False job promises;
- Recruitment in madrassas during prayers or study of the Koran;
- False promises of scholarships abroad;
- Enticement through false promises to pay high monetary values;
- According to local sources, there were two types of training camps:
 - Interns: in the district of Macomia (Mucojo); in Mocímboa da Praia (in the backyards of the group leaders' houses); in Montepuez (Namanhumbir);
 - External: in Tanzania (Kibiti) and in the Great Lakes region;
 - Internally they were trained by PRM agents expelled from the corporation and border guard agents;
 - Externally they are trained by ex-Islamic State fighters who form militias, particularly in the Great Lakes region.

Here, militia chiefs were hired by the Al Shabaab network in Tanzania, Kenya and Somalia to train recruits leaving northern Mozambique.

7 -

The money comes essentially from two sources:

- illicit activities (wood, charcoal, ivory, rubies);
- outside and inside donations. Outside donations come from people with connections to the group's leaders in Mocímboa da Praia. The transfers of monetary values are made electronically: Mpesa, Mkesh, Mmola.
- Of the two sources mentioned, the first (illegal activities) is that it moves large sums of money to finance the group. The trade in wood, ivory and rubies, mainly, is part of an illicit international trade network, involving other actors, not only Tanzanian and Great Lakes, but also Chinese, Vietnamese, etc.
- Personal support for members and their families;
- Funding for travel by spiritual leaders from Tanzania to Mocímboa da Praia;
- Recruitment to recruit new members, through loans to finance small businesses;
- Financing of the group's advertising (reproduction of videos by the Kenyan sheikh Abudo Rogo Mohammed);
- Purchase of armaments in informal internal and external networks.

8 -

Community reaction

- At the level of local administrations, the reactions were different...
- While in Chiúre and Montepuez there was a quick reaction on the part of the local administration, in Mocímboa da Praia it was different because there was a strong penetration of the group's leaders in the local social fabric;
- In addition, the local administration was afraid to interfere in the matter, under the pretext that it was purely internal to mosques.

9 -

Attack motivations

- The establishment of the Islamic state in the region;
- The implementation of Sharia;
- Retaliation against national and foreign citizens for the loss of monetary values and valuable assets expropriated during operations against the illegal exploitation of minerals.

10 -

Ideology of groups

It is characterized by Islamic extremism.

They advocate that citizens:

- You must not pay taxes or participate in electoral processes;
- You must not have an Identity Card;
- You should not go to hospitals when you are sick;
- You must not attend official schools and receive formal education except in Madrassas and mosques;
- You must not participate in government activities or use the metical;
- Should not live with civil servants, as the government is a café (unbeliever).
- Although, the facts show that the main motivations of the attacks are of religious origin, the existence of mineral resources in the region and the possibility of this becoming the future el dourado are important elements of analysis of the motivations

of the attacks because history shows that countries Mineral resource holders have been potential targets for groups for the purpose of exploiting them.

- The first scenario that can be advanced is that mercenaries are probably being hired to destabilize the region so that it is “unprotected”, in order to allow the uncontrolled exploitation or looting of existing mineral resources.

This fact may have some basis given the heterogeneity regarding the nationality of the groups. Mostly Mozambican, Tanzanian, Burundian, South African, Indian, Ugandan, Congolese and Kenyan, Syrian and Iraqi.

- The rhetorical question that arises is, do all evildoers share the same ideology, being individuals of different nationalities?

- The second scenario concerns the existence of groups of illegal gold miners, particularly foreigners, who have been carrying out their activities for a long time and currently have been banned from doing so due to the exploration projects approved by the government.

- Another aspect that should not be overlooked is the fact that a foreign citizen has proposed the Defence and Security Forces to provide security services in this region, ensuring the restoration of Public Order and Tranquillity within one month.

From this, the following conclusion can be drawn, that these actions may have in view the expansion of private international security companies that would be responsible for security in these districts to the detriment of national defence and security forces whose activity constitutes one of the means of demonstration and affirming national sovereignty.

Finally, it can be said that the practice of these acts may be associated with international drug trafficking, using the coastline of the province of Cabo Delgado as one of the main points of entry and exit of drugs from Mozambican territory.

These types of acts have no religious or political ideological motivations, they are criminal organizations that probably resort to this arsenal of macabre acts to ensure the introduction of drugs from Asian countries, into Mozambican territory. The possibility is raised that part of the dividends resulting from drug trafficking will be channelled to finance these attacks.

11 -

Composition and structure of groups

Heterogeneous groups: Mozambicans, Tanzanians, Burundians, South Africans, Indians, Ugandans, Congolese, Kenyan Iraqis, Syrians and Somalia.

- There is a chain of command:
 - They are well structured and properly organized groups, there is a hierarchy of activities and a clear definition of tasks, which presupposes an armed organization with an organized crime charisma.

The Defence and Security Forces destroyed bases and camps located in Chicodi, Inhede, Naneia and Chingalola, all deployed in the District of Mocímboa da Praia.

It should be noted that, the first campsites installed housed those recruited for relatively long periods, of at least two months.

However, due to the reaction of the Defence and Security forces present in the place, the groups of criminals became nomads, settling in the identified places for short periods that varied from one to three weeks.

Likewise, they abandon their camps, moving from one point to the other, whenever a recruited person leaves the camp or, when their cronies are detained by members of the Defense and Security Forces.

12 -

Targets

- The targets were selected by specific criteria:
 - Civilian populations;
 - Elements of government;
 - Public and private institutions (particularly housing);
 - Foreign individuals and companies mainly Portuguese and French

13 -

May 2020 ISIS troops occupied Macomia and hoisted the Islamic State flag. The local squad was robbed and appropriated weapons.

The presence of South African mercenaries in the province of Cabo Delgado, in northern Mozambique, is causing apprehension in Pretoria and "cooling" relations between the two countries. According to professor of international law André Thomashausen, this presence in Cabo Delgado is worrying South Africa, because it was "illegal".

In the past, it was a scandal in South Africa when it became known that the country's mercenaries were fighting against radical group Boko Haram in Nigeria or against militants from al-Shabab in Somalia. South African legislation "very clearly controls and

governs" the provision of "military services by private individuals in foreign countries", adds Thomashausen, who is German and has lived and worked in South Africa for several decades.

"Evidently, South Africa does not want to have a dirty name, with former soldiers, ex-apartheid soldiers, creating confusing and violent situations in neighboring countries, and without really having an agreement on such a measure" , stresses Thomashausen.

14 -

Covid-19: An obstacle in the ongoing negotiations

For now, there is still no agreement in sight between the two countries. Over the weekend, South Africa's public radio and television chain, SABC, advanced, without citing official data, that Mozambique would have asked for air and naval support to fight the insurgency in Cabo Delgado.

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